

Artifact submission #40

Paper: Generic Go to Go: Dictionary-Passing, Monomorphisation, and Hybrid

This document is to help users reproduce the results we reported in our submission.

Artifact Overview

In our paper, we first introduced a dictionary translation for FGG with formal methods, then benchmarked different implementations of Go with generics. The implementations that we benchmarked in the paper are listed in the following table:

implementation	name in the paper	name in the artifact
go2go prototype	go2go	go2go
Go 1.18	Go 1.18	gotip
FGG monomorphisation translator	mono	mono
FGG dictionary passing translator	dict	dict
FGG erasure translator	erasure	dyn

For artifact evaluation, we release (1) our `dict` implementation, (2) our `erasure` implementation, and (3) the benchmark set.

Installation

The artifact has been configured as a docker container. Please check HotCRP for the download link and the checksum.

The container can be installed by

```
sudo docker import oopsla-submission-418.tar oopsla-submission-418:main
```

Then, you can run the docker image by

```
sudo docker run -it oopsla-submission-418:main bash
```

Implementations (Section 6.1 of the paper)

The source code for `erasure` is under

```
~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/internal/fgg/dyn
```

The source code for `dict` is under

```
~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/internal/fgg/dictpass
```

Both implementations are implemented under our fork of FGG source tree. We rename it as FCGG in our implementation.

Here's an example of using a precompiled one at `~/go/bin/fcgg` to translate an example using `dict`:

```
~/go/bin/fcgg -fgg -dictpassnoassertion -- \  
~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-real-world-benchmarks\  
/pizza-benchmarks/cell/cell.fgg 2>/dev/null
```

Here's an example of using a precompiled one at `~/go/bin/fcgg` to translate an example using `erasure`:

```
~/go/bin/fcgg -fgg -dynamic -- \  
~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-real-world-benchmarks\  
/pizza-benchmarks/cell/cell.fgg 2>/dev/null
```

Reproducing Fig. 17 & 18

Before running the benchmarks, please run

```
export PATH="/usr/local/go/bin:${PATH}"
```

Instruction Count

Figure 17 (a)

```
cd ~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-micro-new/binary_code_size  
bash fig17.sh
```

output explanation:

```
n erasure dict mono go2go g118  
PARAM_N = 2..40  
2 514 488 1050 920 472  
...
```

The first line shows the column name of the output. The second line tells we measure when n changes from 2 to 40, which means we measure program (a) for Fig. 17.

Figure 18 (a)

```
cd ~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-micro-new/binary_code_size  
bash fig18.sh
```

The output is similar to fig17.sh.

Execution Time

Figure 17 (b)

We first forward the output to a text file:

```
cd ~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-micro-new/exec_time_new  
bash fig17.sh > fig17.txt
```

In fig17.txt, in each line we show the time of each implementation executing 10 times, with their name showing before the 10 numbers. We use a helper script to compute the average:

```
python3 ../compute_avg.py ./fig17.txt multi
```

Figure 18 (b)

The commands are similar to Figure 17 (b).

```
cd ~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-micro-new/exec_time_new  
bash fig18.sh > fig18.txt
```

```
python3 ../compute_avg.py ./fig18.txt multi
```

Compilation Time

Figure 17 (c)

```
cd ~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-micro-new/compile_time_new
bash fig17.sh > fig17.txt

python3 ../compute_avg.py ./fig17.txt multi
```

Figure 18 (c)

```
cd ~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-micro-new/compile_time_new
bash fig18.sh > fig18.txt

python3 ../compute_avg.py ./fig18.txt multi
```

Remarks

For the execution time and compilation time, the results can be different on different hardware configurations. All time units are microsecond (μs).

Reproducing program (b)-(d)

The scripts are named as `program_b.sh`, `program_c.sh`, and `program_d.sh` under the same location as `fig17.sh` and `fig18.sh`, and can be executed similarly as above.

Reproducing Table 1

Compilation Time (The last group of columns)

The command:

```
cd ~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-real-world-benchmarks
bash compile_time.sh > compile_time.txt
python3 compute_avg.py compile_time.txt
```

The output:

```
oopsla-real-world-benchmarks# python3 compute_avg.py compile_time.txt
list
mono 298203.4
dict_no_cast 299916.6
dyn 305875.3
go2go 321387.5
gotip 283027.8
resizable_array
mono 307961.6
dict_no_cast 303938.9
dyn 303147.6
go2go 308102.1
gotip 318453.4
list_reverse
mono 329901.8
dict_no_cast 317441.6
dyn 310202.7
go2go 309356.6
gotip 291644.1
```

...

The above output shows the average compilation time for the benchmark `List` in microseconds. Here, `dict_no_cast` indicates `dict` in the above benchmarks.

Execution Time (The group of columns in middle)

The command:

```
cd ~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-real-world-benchmarks
bash execution_time.sh > execution_time.txt
python3 compute_avg.py execution_time.txt
```

The output is similar to compilation time.

Instruction Count (The first group of columns)

```
cd ~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-real-world-benchmarks
bash code_size.sh
```

Reproducing coefficients

See this [Google Colab document](https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1-Jb4PrXUp2xpluFXSf9OpPmK8LzkQWnF?usp=sharing) <https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1-Jb4PrXUp2xpluFXSf9OpPmK8LzkQWnF?usp=sharing>.

Reproducing the cache miss results

This is to reproduce the results reported between line 944-946 in the paper. 1. Install `perf` tool in the docker. Because it depends on the Linux kernel version, we didn't include it in the docker image.

```
apt install linux-tools-common linux-tools-generic
```

2. generate the executables:

```
cd ~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-micro-new/compile_time_new
bash cache_miss.sh
```

3. run the executables with `perf`:

```
cd tmp_exe_files
perf stat -e cache-misses ./tmp-dictpassnoassertion-m_exp-9-1
perf stat -e cache-misses ./tmp-monomc-m_exp-9-1
```

Remark: some platforms may not support measuring cache misses.

Reproducing results for type simulation

```
cd ~/go/src/github.com/sfzhu93/fcgg/benchmark/oopsla-micro-new/exec_time_new
bash type_simulation.sh > type_simulation.txt
python3 ../compute_avg.py type_simulation.txt multi
```

The result confirms “the translated programs become significantly slower (e.g., 2.3X slower for (a) when configuring n equal to 2)”, line 948.